

amount of virus antigen in the extracts was determined by their absorbance at 405 nm after 30-min incubation with the substrate.

Absorbance decreased as extracts were diluted and RSV was detected in the extracts up to 1/400-1-3200 dilution (by weight) (see figure). The relative amount of RSV was shown as absorbance of ex-

tracts at 1/200 dilution for the test at 30 and 45 d after inoculation and at 1/160 dilution at 60 d.

The relative amount of RSV in individual plants varied among test varieties. Statistically significant differences in the amount of RSV was shown at 30 d after inoculation, but not at 45 and 60 d. Regardless of the test variety, the amount

of RSV was highest at 45 d and declined by 60 d. The relative amount of RSV was less in Ptb 21 and Murungakayan than in the other varieties. There was no significant difference in RSV amount between resistant and susceptible varieties. The results indicate that the resistant varieties tested were resistant to RSV infection but not to virus multiplication. □

Rice grassy stunt (GSV) at high altitudes

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The occurrence of GSV and its transmission by the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* were reported in India in 1969. About 100 ha of rice in Tamil Nadu were infected with GSV in 1972, and about 15,000 ha were infested by the virus and its vector in the adjoining state of Kerala in 1973-74.

Since then, the disease has not been observed, despite the presence of large BPH populations. Recently, rice with symptoms similar to those of GSV was found in the Dugalur Valley of the Nilgiris Mountains of Tamil Nadu, where rice is grown on about 3,500 ha. The valley is isolated, and surrounded by 2,000-m-high, densely forested hills. BPH are present in the valley.

Disease symptoms were severe stunting and profuse tillering with narrow erect

leaves, but the plants were green because of high soil N in the valley. Infection was less than 3% in Jagannath, IR20, and local varieties on the horticultural farm in Devala.

Transmission tests using BPH nymphs were conducted. Nymphs lived for 10 d on the source plant, then were transferred to 10-d-old TN1 plants for 5-d inoculation access feeding. One month later, inoculated TN1 plants developed GSV symptoms. □

Pest management and control INSECTS

Brown planthopper (BPH) resistance to a synthetic pyrethroid

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As a follow-up of the 1979-80 survey that indicated BPH was resistant to permethrin yet susceptible to fenvalerate, in 1982 we monitored BPH susceptibility to four major synthetic pyrethroids and DDT.

Up to 1,000-fold resistance to permethrin was found while resistance levels to 3 other synthetic pyrethroids were much lower, ranging from 10- to 50-fold (see table). All BPH tested were suscepti-

Susceptibility of a susceptible (S) and 6 field strains of BPH to 4 synthetic pyrethroids and DDT in Taiwan, China.^a

Strain	Permethrin		Cypermethrin		Deltamethrin		Fenvalerate		DDT	
	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	RR	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	RR	LC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	RR	LC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	RR	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	RR
Pingtung	2.53	843	9.17	26	14.6	15	5.32	16	—	—
Meinung	2.38	793	5.53	15	39.2	41	13.22	40	0.121	3.7
Hsinshih	3.27	1090	7.53	21	6.7	7	16.67	51	0.114	3.5
Chiayi	2.15	717	4.00	11	9.1	10	4.70	14	0.112	3.4
Taichung	0.22	73	0.48	1	2.0	2	2.30	7	0.062	1.9
Hsinchu	2.64	880	5.29	15	14.3	15	4.80	15	0.128	3.9
S	0.003	—	0.36	—	0.95	—	0.33	—	0.022	—

^a Resistance ratio (RR) = LC₅₀ of field strain divided by LC₅₀ of S strain.

ble to DDT, giving circumstantial evidence that in Taiwan BPH resistance to permethrin is not related to DDT resistance, as it is in insects such as the

housefly, mosquito, and diamondback moth. A metabolic mechanism probably has caused the high BPH resistance to permethrin. □

Changing insect pest status in the Imphal Valley

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Expanding irrigation facilities in the Imphal Valley allow the growing of two rice crops instead of one. But as cropping

intensity increased, so have populations of common insect pests and sporadic outbreaks of unusual pests.

In 1979, a dry year, stem borers were major pests (see table), with 9.5% dead-hearts at tillering and 16.7% at post-flowering. As rice hectareage increased, populations of other insects such as gall midge, leafroller, leafhoppers, caseworm, grasshoppers, rice bugs, and greenhorned

caterpillar increased, and pest problems developed earlier in the season.

Caseworm became a serious problem when main crop transplanting was delayed to mid-Aug, and gall midge became a problem after the last week of Jul. Leafroller and greenhorned caterpillar disappeared late in the main season, and leafhoppers, grasshoppers, and rice bugs continued through harvest. Thrips

Insect pests of rice in the Imphal Valley of Manipur, India.

Pest and year of severity	Family	Economic status	Damage ^a
Stem borer, 1979 <i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> (Walk)	Pyrilidae	Major pests in dry season. Collectively, become major in upland rice.	9.7% DH at preflowering and 16.7% at postflowering, 10 Apr 1979.
<i>S. innotata</i> (Walk)	Pyrilidae		
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i> (Walk)	Pyrilidae		
<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walk)	Noctuidae		
Gall midge, 1981–82 <i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (Wood-Mason)	Cecidomyiidae	Major pest in the main season, particularly in late transplanted rice.	11.1% SS on 11 Aug 1981 transplanting.
Green leafhopper, 1980–82 <i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Dist.)	Cicadellidae	Major pests in the main season.	7.0 GLH/5 sweeps on 11 Aug 1981 transplanting.
<i>N. nigropictus</i> (Stal)	Cicadellidae		
Leafroller, 1979–83 <i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guen.)	Pyrilidae	Major pest in the main season	22.5 LR/m ² on 8 Jul 1981 transplanting
Caseworm, 1980–82 <i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> Guen.	Pyrilidae	Serious pests in flood-prone areas in late transplanted main season rice.	72.25 CW/m ² on 24 Aug 1981 transplanting.
Grasshopper, 1980–82 <i>Oxya japonica</i> Thunberg	Acrididae	Major pest. Population increases as season advances.	3.0 GH/5 sweeps on 11 Aug 1981 transplanting.
Rice bug, 1980–82 <i>Leprocorisa oratorius</i> (Fab.)	Alydidae	Major pest. Population increases as season advances.	1.0 RB/5 sweeps on 11 Aug 1981 transplanting.
<i>Cletus</i> sp.	Coreidae		
Whorl maggot, 1980–83 <i>Hydrellia</i> sp.	Ephydriidae	Major pest in early and main season rice.	13.96% tiller infestation 15 DT on 1 Jun 1982 transplanting.
Planthoppers, 1980–83 <i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horvath)	Delphacidae	Major pests in early paddy only.	407.25 WBPH/m ² 45 DT on 15 Apr 1982 transplanting.
<i>Sogatodes pusanus</i> (Dist.)	Delphacidae		
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stål)	Delphacidae		
Nursery thrips, 1980–83 <i>Stenchaetothrips biformis</i> (Bagnall)	Thripidae	Major pest of main season nursery.	179.5 nymphs/5 sweeps 15 DT on 1 Aug 1982 sown nursery.
Greenhorned caterpillar, 1980–82 <i>Melanitis leda</i> Linn.	Nymphalidae	Major pest early in the main season.	2.5 GC/5 sweeps on 14 Jul 1981 transplanting.
Ear-cutting caterpillar, 1982 <i>Mythimna separata</i> (Walk)	Noctuidae	Sporadic pest late in the rice season.	10.9 immature insects/hill on Oct 1982 planting of RCM3.

^a DH = deadhearts, SS = silvershoots, GLH = green leafhopper, LR = leafroller, CW = caseworm, GH = grasshopper, KB = rice bug, DT = days after transplanting, WBPH = whitebacked planthopper, GC = greenhorned caterpillar. The data show peak activity of the pest on P33 at the ICAR Complex farm at Sangaipat. SS and LR are average of 6 observations; CW, GH, GLH, KB, and HC are average of 5 observations at 15-d interval, starting from 15 DT.

damaged Jul and Aug nurseries in valleys, but not in the foothills.

In 1980, whorl maggot in the main season and whitebacked planthopper in

early rice were abundant. The whitebacked planthopper seriously damaged early rice in 1983, perhaps because of unusually heavy rains and flooding. □

A meadow grasshopper *Conocephalus longipennis* (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae) predator of rice yellow stem borer (YSB) egg masses

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Experiments to determine the egg parasitization incidence of YSB by taping egg masses to plants in the field revealed a high level of predation by an unknown insect.

Suspected predators were collected and caged with potted rice plants laden with stem borer egg masses. Adults of a meadow grasshopper, *Conocephalus longipennis* (Haan), produced identical predation symptoms as those found in the field.

Subsequent field trials using marked egg masses showed predation ranged from 17 to 65% over the sampling dates, with an overall average of 46% (see table). □

Rate of predation of *Scirpophaga incertulas* egg masses by *Conocephalus longipennis*, IRRRI, 1980-81.

Date egg masses were exposed	Egg masses exposed (no.)	Predation (%)
6 Nov 1980	24	17
28 Nov 1980	32	25
7 Jan 1981	72	65
14 Jan 1981	24	45
17 Sep 1981	28	46
28 Sep 1981	40	60
9 Oct 1981	52	65

Incidence of brown planthopper (BPH) and white fly in Nigeria

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In Mar and Apr 1983, BPH *Nilaparvata maеander* Fennah caused hopperburn in two rice fields at Ibadan, Nigeria. This is the first report of hopperburn caused by *N. maеander* in Africa. Some of the affected cultivars were TOs 5262, TOs 6860, TOx 1727-B, TOx 1812-B, TOg 6344, TOg 6399, and TOg 6745.

Mind bugs *Cyrtorhinus menanops* Reuter and *Tytthus parviceps* Reuter are